

TEACHING VOCABULARY FOR DIFFERENT AGES

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***Abstract** In this article, we studied several methods and strategies of teaching vocabulary for different age groups. This article explains how to teaching vocabulary can be effective and fun, applying interactive activities, and word games. There are given recommendations how to organize vocabulary teaching lessons with the help of modern pedagogical methods and techniques, such as using internet database, apps, videos and graphic organizers.*

***Key words:** vocabulary, lexical resources, teaching explicitly, graphic organizer, real-world context, modern pedagogical methods.*

Introduction

It is hard for language learners to read and understand a text if they do not know what the words mean. A solid vocabulary boosts reading comprehension for learners of all ages. The more words students know, the better they understand the text. That's why effective vocabulary teaching is so important, especially for students who learn and think differently and refer to different age groups.

The goal of vocabulary teaching strategies are not just to increase language learners' vocabulary. Whilst, it is to make sure the words are meaningful and relevant to their lives. Vocabulary is the basis for learning any languages. Educational research shows that vocabulary strongly relates to reading comprehension, intelligence, general ability and age. As children learn to read, they must learn to decode (sound-out) print, but they also must have a vocabulary base (word knowledge) in order to make sense of what they decode. By third grade, however, children are reading to learn. For example, a child who is reading to learn

about “weather” needs to know words like *hot, cold, rain, snow, chilly, freezing, thunderstorm, rainbow* and *lightening* (a basic vocabulary) to understand the topic. At the same time, however, the child will likely learn new words like *freezing, lightening, thunderstorm* — continuing to build his/her vocabulary. While we are teaching children vocabulary there are some useful techniques:

1. Read to your child a lot;
2. Using colorful and eye-catching materials;
3. Providing with several dictionary books and cards;
4. Communicate with a child about a theme studied;
5. Use songs, videos and cartoon to learn new words.

When we consider about teaching vocabulary for adults there are a number of strategies which makes learning process effective.

1. *Choosing a text.* Find an appropriate text (or multiple texts for students to choose from) that includes the vocabulary words you want to teach. The text must be appropriate to their interest and age features.

2. *Using imagination to find definitions.* Find resources you and your learners can consult to come up with a definition for each word. The definition should be easy to understand, be written in everyday language, and capture the word’s common use. Your definitions can include pictures, videos, or other multimedia options.

3. *Teaching new words with the help of visual aids.* Say the word aloud and have students repeat the word. For visual support, display the words and their definitions for students to see, such as on a word wall, flip chart, or vocabulary graphic organizer. Showing pictures related to the word can be helpful, too.

4. *Recalling.* Allow time for students to reflect on what they know or don’t know about the words. Remember that your class will come to the lesson with varying levels of vocabulary knowledge. Some students may be familiar with some of the words. Other students may not know any of them. If time permits, this could be a good opportunity to use flexible grouping so students can work on different words.

5. *Implementing interesting and fun post-activities to illustrate the meaning of all new words of a lesson.* After reading, use one or more of the following activities to help students learn the words more effectively: Word associations, Use your senses, Picture perfect and etc.

6. *Play word games.* Throughout the week, play word games like vocabulary bingo, vocabulary Pictionary, and charades to practice the new words. Include words you've taught in the past for additional reinforcement.

7. *Involving students to use new words in their daily speech.* They can use their new vocabulary in different contexts, like at home, at recess, or during afterschool activities. Consider asking students to use a vocabulary notebook to jot down when they use the words. Praise students when you hear them using those words in and out of the classroom.

Conclusion

Just learning and repeating (“skill and drill”) cannot help to teach new words and increase learners’ lexical resources. Language learners acquire new words when they experience several methods that use easy-to-understand definitions. Choosing an appropriate method of teaching vocabulary for different age groups is a crucial step of successful learning. While studying a new word students must not be only aware of its lexical meaning, but also they should image it, corporate it with a real-life situation and use them in real-life context.

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